

Anomaly-Based Intrusion Detection System: A modern Perspective

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Abstract---Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) are beneficial for providing security against malicious activities for the users. Attackers find new ways to send malicious packets without the detection of Traditional Signature Based IDS. Anomaly based intrusion detection systems using Machine Learning are hence being researched for feasibility and there are many models that have successfully classified the benchmark dataset NSL-KDD but very few research papers have used UNB-IDS 2018. Hence, the approach used is to build a model that tries to successfully classify whether it is malicious or benign with labelled packet information from both the datasets and compare them. Two datasets (A benchmark dataset and a New and a Larger Dataset) are used to train the Machine Learning Classifiers and a sufficient testing accuracy of 90 percent and above with Random Forests was achieved. The robustness of the model is tested against FGSM, JSMA and novel adversarial inputs using GANs. The model trained with NSL-KDD dataset showed significant decrease in prediction accuracy against adversarial inputs while the Model trained with UNB-IDS Dataset is robust against adversarial inputs.

Keywords: Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS); anomaly-based detection; NSL-KDD; UNB-IDS 2018; Random Forest; adversarial attacks; GANs; FGSM; JSMA.

1. INTRODUCTION

Computer Networks as we see in today's world have become much more vulnerable than they have been ever before. Attackers try to make use of these vulnerabilities and try out various kinds of attacks like buffer overflow attacks, traffic flooding, Denial of Service etc. All these kinds of attacks are possible because of the malicious network packets passing through the institutional or organizational network. In such a scenario, Network Intrusion Detection systems play an important role in avoiding such attacks. An Intrusion Detection system is a detection system put in place to monitor computer networks. The main purpose of these systems is to detect if the network packet entering the institutional network is a legitimate packet or a malicious packet. This kind of detection helps in preventing some of the major attacks which can take place if the malicious packet enters the network.

Intrusion Detection systems can be mainly implemented in two ways, that is the signature-based Intrusion Detection System and Anomaly based Intrusion Detection System.

1. Signature based IDS mainly works on the different kinds of patterns which are identified through the intrusions which have already taken place in the past. The IDS compares the incoming packets with the existing patterns and compares to checks if it matches with any of those patterns. If it does match it is considered as an intrusion.
2. Anomaly based IDS work slightly differently than the signature-based IDS as it does not depend on the existing patterns but tries to identify deviations or any malicious activity which is not normally seen in

the legitimate packets. In this way the anomaly-based IDS can identify intrusions even if the particular kind is never seen before. For such IDS's advanced machine learning techniques are used to identify deviations in the packets from legitimate ones.

Another aspect of the network attacks that place are the attacks with adversarial inputs. An adversary is a small perturbation or noise that is added to the malicious network packet to make the IDS model misclassify it as a legitimate packet. The IDS model would not be able to sense the small perturbations in the input to classify as an anomaly. This poses a great security threat to the networks.

Figure 1 Adding Adversary to an image causing IDS to misclassify.

Our main focus in this project is to develop an Anomaly based IDS using advanced machine learning techniques and to obtain a robust Intrusion Detection System model against the adversarial inputs.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Many existing Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) are predominantly based on signature-based models. While these systems are effective for identifying known threats, they struggle to detect new or evolving attack patterns. Anomaly-based Intrusion Detection Systems (AIDS) have garnered limited research attention, with most models relying on the NSL-KDD dataset, an outdated dataset dating back to 1999. This reliance limits their ability to generalize to modern network traffic patterns and threats. Current anomaly-based IDS also face several challenges. One notable drawback is the high false positive rate, where previously unknown but legitimate behaviours are mistakenly flagged as malicious. This can disrupt network operations and reduce system reliability. Additionally, adversarial inputs, which involve subtle perturbations in data, pose a significant challenge by causing models to misclassify network packets.

The primary objective of this project is to develop a robust anomaly-based IDS using advanced machine learning algorithms. Our model aims to improve resilience against adversarial inputs while maintaining high accuracy in distinguishing malicious and benign traffic. Furthermore, given the lack of pre-existing adversarial inputs for testing IDS robustness, our work also focuses on generating novel adversarial inputs from network packet data. These inputs will serve as a benchmark for evaluating the robustness of IDS models, using techniques discussed in the literature survey.

Internal estimates in random forests track error rates, individual tree strength, and inter-tree correlation, allowing for analysis of the effects of varying the number of features used in node splitting. These estimates are also employed to assess the importance of variables in the model. The approach is applicable not only to classification tasks but also to regression problems.

Ensembles in random forests are formed by generating random vectors to influence tree construction. For example, in bagging, subsets of the training set are selected randomly without replacement. Similarly, methods like random split selection identify potential splits at each node, and other techniques employ random weights or subspaces of features to grow trees. The foundational principle remains consistent: for each tree, a random vector is generated independently from previous vectors, guiding the training process and resulting in a

classifier that votes for the most popular class. When the votes of all trees are aggregated, the final classification decision is made.

This methodology has been shown to significantly improve classification accuracy, with its roots in methods like bagging and random subspace selection. Notable contributions, such as those focusing on geometric feature selection and random split generation, have influenced the evolution of random forests, making them a robust tool in both classification and regression tasks.

3. LITERATURE SURVEY

3.1 Securess of Machine Learning NIDS [1]

Machine learning models have been successfully used in various domains but recently, there have been some methods to fool these machines learning based models in classifying them incorrectly and these are explained in Rupam Kumar Sharma et.[1]

Authors have created models like SVM, SOM etc which are trained continuously by incoming packets into the network and have tested them against the inputs which were tampered(poisoned) by making some minute changes in their feature values. As a result, these models drastically started performing under the acceptable level by wrongly classifying the inputs.

The dataset was analysed to find the features which influence decision making the most and those were tampered with. New packets were created using Scapy utility in python and injected into the training of NIDS classifier.

These poisoned inputs shifted the decision boundaries of the classifiers drastically influencing their results. This led them to classifying malignant packets as benign.

Figure 2 Support Vectors with Normal Kernel

But authors haven't tried testing the adversarial inputs into the training of the ANN models. And they have manually tried to identify features for poisoning in the packets.

The features for tampering can be found by JSMA technique by identifying the features which have maximum gradient towards decision making.

3.2 Metrics to achieve robustness for a Machine Learning Model[2]

Machine Learning models trained work well with unseen inputs due to statistical similarity. Models could wrongly classify the inputs if used in real time due to a different medium of measuring the parameters or due to slight changes in values not changing the data point majorly. Adversarial Inputs Generation Methods are of two types : White Box(Gradient based) and Black Box scenario. Nicolas et al. [2] explained about L-BFGS, FGSM and JSMA in white box scenarios. L-BFGS was a brute force approach that minimizes perturbation. FGSM tries to find the direction of maximum prediction error in the model. JSMA makes use of the saliency value of inputs. Substitute model in the Black Box scenario where the model logic and structure is unknown tries to replicate the model and generate adversarial inputs making use of a property called transferability.

Nicolas et al. [2] also discussed different defences against Adversarial Inputs like Adversarial input training and Defensive Distillation[8]. Though they can still be broken by Black Box attacks and Computationally expensive attacks. Nicolas et al.[2] mention the lack of security testing methods other than SMT Solver and Reluplex that only determine output labels are constant across a desired neighbourhood. Cleverhans library can be used for generation of adversarial inputs to check model robustness. Figure 3 represents the relation of different adversarial goals and attacker knowledge about the model with respect to the robustness.

Figure 3. Graph to represent attack difficulty w.r.t. Knowledge of model used and the goal of the adversary [2].

3.3 Intrusion Detection System using a combination of GAN and AE [3]

Supervised learning requires a huge amount of data to train the model in which there is a lot of human labour involved in preparing the data, extracting the information from the data and labelling them. This paper by Kazuki Hara et. al address this issue and describe the idea of using semi supervised learning which significantly uses unlabeled data than labelled in training.

This particular model architecture consists of AAE which uses semi supervised learning technique which is a combination of GAN and AE trained on NSL-KDD dataset. Here the AE is used as a generator and 2 Discriminators which discriminate the data generated by the Generator. GAN is a combination of generator and discriminator which mainly reduces the dimension features in the hidden layer. The encoder generates two latent variable vectors z_1 and z_2 to hold the features of input data. The following is the data held by z_1 and z_2 :

- 1) z_1 - categorical distribution (“normal” or “attack”)
- 2) z_2 - other important non discrete features, Gaussian distribution

Figure 4.Architecture of the Semi supervised learning model using auto Encoder and GANS.[3].

The paper also describes the different accuracies measured. Figure 5 below describes the various accuracies mentioned. The accuracies are measured with various proportions of labelled and unlabelled data starting from 90% labelling rate to as low as 0.01 labelling rate.

RESULTS OF ACCURACY COMPARISON(AAEDNN)

Labeling Rate	90%	10%	1%	0.10%	0.01%
Labeled Data	113,375	12,597	1,259	125	11
Unlabeled Data	12,598	113,376	124,714	125,848	125,962
Adversarial Autoencoder	83.20	83.11	82.78	81.37	53.66
Deep neural network	81.07	77.33	75.88	76.87	71.55

Figure 5. Accuracy measures with varying amounts of labelled data

The advantages of the described model are:

1. It works with least labelled data
2. Higher accuracies and at par with present existing IDS models

The disadvantages of the described model are:

1. A much more complex model using 2 different types of neural network
2. Takes a lot of time for training the model

3.4 Effective Adversarial Inputs against DNN based IDS[4]

Traditional IDS systems were based on a set of rules which failed to work against new attacks. And used to have a high false positive rate, but now IDS systems are based on ML techniques especially DNN models as they are more tolerant to unseen attacks. But recently they have been found to be vulnerable against adversarial inputs. Many black box attacks such as substitute model based attack, ZOO, GANs etc have been explained by Kaichen Yang et. al[4]. These models were tried against a DNN based NIDS trained on an NSL-KDD dataset created by them.

Each method brought down the performance of the model drastically, but the most impact was seen in ZOO where F1-score metric went down to 0.273.

TABLE IV
IMPACT OF ATTACK BASED ON ZOO

Technique	AC	PC	RC	FA	Fscore
Target model	0.890	0.897	0.900	0.100	0.898
Target model under attack	0.537	0.634	0.173	0.100	0.273

Figure 6 Metrics impacted after Adversarial Attack on DNN - NIDS model

Authors have tried only sigmoid functions in the ZOO, which can be tested with other functions like tanh, etc. And the GANs model tried to utilize only linear layers which could have been replaced with dense layers.

3.5 Adversarial Deep Learning Against Intrusion Detection Classifiers [5]

Machine learning models are being developed and used in many real-world applications and have been successful for their accuracy and performance. Many of these models are now being used in critical applications where there is very little room for error without thinking of the security. But in recent times the machine learning models have been proven not to be secure and face Adversarial inputs.

Simple ML algorithms were used on NSL-KDD dataset to generate NIDS models and all models showed an accuracy of around 75%. For adversarial input generation, FGSM and JSMA models are very relevant, but the author tested only the adversarial samples generated by the JSMA method on baseline models because it is assumed by the author that FGSM samples were not applicable practically.

Using the perturbation percentage of 6.25% between the original and the adversarial samples, the author reduced the accuracy of the models by about 5% to 28%.

The methodology chosen for this study was based on Big Data Analytics (BDA) because the data is dynamic and follows three V's of Big Data. Also, an iterative process was used in this study mainly because the whole process repeated itself right from data preprocessing, modelling to evaluation. This makes this study reproducible in the current scenario.

3.6 Toward Generating a New Intrusion Detection Dataset and Intrusion Traffic Characterization - Iman Sharafaldin, Arash Habibi Lashkari and Ali A. Ghorbani [6]

As the datasets for the Intrusion Detection Systems are very vast with different types of attacks and packets coming through various machines there is a need for analyzing the dataset, characterizing and distinguishing different attack profiles. Such Datasets cannot be shared because of the privacy aspect that comes into place and even the available data is anonymized. Due to these reasons there is a lack of statistical analysis and characterization on these datasets. This gives rise to the need for creating a benchmark dataset and analyzing all the attack profiles of the dataset.

According to the last research and proposed evaluation framework, eleven characteristics, namely Attack Diversity, Anonymity, Available Protocols, Complete Capture, Complete Interaction, Complete Network Configuration, Complete Traffic, Feature Set, Heterogeneity, Labelling, and Metadata are critical for a comprehensive and valid IDS dataset.

Attacks based on 7 common attack profiles were performed which include Brute Force Attack, Heartbleed Attack, Botnet, DoS Attack, DDoS Attack, Web Attack, Infiltration Attack.

In the paper evaluation is shown in a four-fold Manner:

1. Extracted 80 traffic features using CIC FlowMeter.
2. Tested the 60 features using RandomForestRegressor to select the best short feature set for each attack which can be best detection features for each attack
3. Examined the performance and accuracy of selected features with common ML algorithms
4. Evaluate the quality of the generated dataset by searching for common mistakes and criticisms of other synthetically created datasets, based on the 11 criteria mentioned previously.

3.7 Popular Machine Learning Techniques used in IDS

3.7.1 Artificial Neural network (ANN)

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) are information processing units designed to mimic the neurons in the human brain. An ANN consists of layers of neurons categorized into input, hidden, and output layers. When used in Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS), neural networks trained on the KDD dataset follow three main phases. They are automated parses, training and testing.

Recent advancements in IDS using ANNs are discussed in [7,8,9].

3.7.2 Support Vector Machines (SVMs)

SVMs, introduced by Cortes and Vapnik, are designed to learn two-class discriminant functions from training data. Key characteristics of SVMs include class separation, overlapping classes, non-linearity and problem solution

Recent studies on IDS using SVMs are highlighted in [10,11,12].

3.7.3 Decision Tree

Given a set of instances, Decision tree classify the instances by sorting them down the tree starting from the root and ending in a leaf of the tree. An attribute of an instance is represented as a node of the tree and each branch descending from the node corresponds to one of the possible values of the attribute. This type of learning is mostly used in cases where instances can be represented by set of attribute and value pairs, the output of the target function is not continuous and map to a discrete set of values, considerations of possible errors in the training set and missing values in the training set. Some of the recent work using Decision Tree in IDS can be found in the following papers [13,14,15].

3.7.4 Random Forest

Random forests are an ensemble learning method that combines multiple tree predictors, where each tree is built based on the values of a random vector sampled independently and identically distributed for all trees

in the forest. As the number of trees increases, the generalization error of the forest converges to a stable limit. This error depends on the strength of individual trees and the correlation among them. By employing a random selection of features to split each node, random forests achieve error rates comparable to Adaboost but exhibit greater robustness to noise.

4. CHALLENGES FACED

4.1 Challenges Faced In Using Machine Learning

Machine Learning has proved to be result promising and many companies such as Amazon uses machine learning for meeting different objectives. However, the success of using machine learning depends on lot of factors of which few are listed below.

4.2.1 Training Data (Explicit and Implicit)

Training data used in a learning algorithm can be broadly newly categorized into implicit feedback data and explicit feedback data. In explicit feedback data, feature vector corresponding to a message packet is explicitly confirmed as an attack or normal without much difficulty, and correspondingly used to train the learning algorithm. However, in implicit feedback, data features might not be possible to immediately be classified as normal or anomaly because more attributes value might resemble a normal data but overall feature vector or set of features vector might correspond to an anomaly. Such “critical tag” need to be considered with utmost care.

4.2.2 High Cost : Errors Running an IDS with even a very small rate of false classification might come with high risk to the organization or institution. Falsely classified as Negative might end up in a remote machine gaining access to the internal network and thereby rendering the entire network nonfunctional. The objective would be to design learning algorithms that could ideally make “False Positive” and “False Negative” parameters approximately approach to zero value.

4.2.3 Rule Generation

For a message or for a given source whose feature vector is classified as abnormal it is critical to judge whether the abnormality corresponds to an attack or a behavior deviating from normal but not an attack. More critical in such cases is automatic rule generation corresponding the feature set of the message or originating source.

4.2.4 Proper interpretation of traffic over time

The variability in the network traffic parameters such as volume of traffic, bandwidth consumption, duration of connections, number of connections can make things more critical in operational environment. Adding to the mentioned facts diversity can also be on the application parameters of the messages, nature of protocols and attribute values of different headers fields. Question arises here is the duration for which a given connection or the network should be monitored or how long duration traffic should be aggregated for evaluation. Application layer DoS attack occurs in slow rate and don't generate massive amount of traffic.

4.2.5 Data set Hindrance

The data set that are publicly available such as KDD Cup 1999, NSL-KDD are almost a decade old. Learning algorithms are still trained on these existing old data sets which fails to incorporate feature vector of recent attacks such as RUDY[R-U-Dead-Yet]. The alternative could be repository of self-monitored network. However, this could be a complicated task due to non-accessibility to an appropriately sized network.

4.2 Challenges in Existing IDS Models:

The current landscape of Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS), particularly anomaly-based models, faces several key challenges that hinder their effectiveness in real-world applications. These challenges, primarily arising from data limitations, algorithmic complexity, and operational constraints, significantly impact the ability of IDS to accurately detect and mitigate emerging threats.

False Positives: A major drawback of current anomaly-based IDS models is the high rate of false positives. Since these models often rely on outdated datasets or narrow feature sets, they can mistakenly flag new, legitimate behaviors as attacks. This results in unnecessary alerts, disruptions in network operations, and increased costs and time for organizations to investigate false alarms. The challenge lies in creating an IDS that can differentiate between legitimate novel behaviors and malicious activities, thereby reducing the false positive rate.

Adversarial Inputs: Another significant challenge is the vulnerability of IDS models to adversarial inputs. Attackers may intentionally introduce small perturbations in network traffic to mislead the system, causing it to misclassify malicious behavior as benign or vice versa. This can undermine the reliability of IDS, especially when the system is exposed to novel attack techniques or subtle manipulations. Defending against such adversarial attacks is critical to ensuring the robustness of IDS models in practical environments.

5. DATASETS

5.1 NSL-KDD Dataset:

The NSL-KDD [16] dataset is a refined version of its predecessor KDD99 dataset. NSL-KDD dataset comprises close to 4,900,000 unique connection vectors, where every connection vector consists of 41 features of which 34 are continuous features and 07 are discrete features. Each vector is labelled as either normal or attack. There are four major categories of attacks labelled in NSL-KDD: denial of service attack, probing attack, users-to-root attack, and remote-to-local attack.

- i. Denial of service attack (DoS): Denial of service is an attack category, which exhausts the victim's assets, thereby making it unable to handle legitimate requests. Examples of DoS attacks are "teardrop," "neptune," "ping of death(pod)," "mail bomb," "back," "smurf," and "land."
- ii. Probing attack (PROBE): Objective of surveillance and other probing attacks is to gain information about the remote victim. Examples of probing attacks are "nmap," "satan," "ipsweep," and "portsweep."
- iii. Users-to-root attack (U2R): The attacker enters into the local system by using the authorized credentials of the victim user and tries to exploit the vulnerabilities to gain the administrator privileges. Examples of U2R attacks are "load module," "buffer overflow," "rootkit," and "perl."
- iv. Remote-to-local attack (R2L): The attackers access the targeted system or network from the remote machine and try to gain the local access of the victim machine. Examples of R2L attacks are "phf," "warezmaster," "warezclient," "spy," "imap," "ftp write," "multihop," and "guess passwd."

5.2 UNB-IDS2018 Dataset:

The UNB-IDS2018 dataset, developed by the University of New Brunswick (UNB), addresses common dataset limitations such as rarity, anonymity, privacy concerns, and lack of statistical characteristics. Generated within a dedicated UNB test network, the dataset captures various attacks, with input features extracted using CICFlowMeter-V3. Simulated protocols include HTTPS, HTTP, POP3, SSH, FTP, IMAP, and SMTP, with a predominance of HTTP and HTTPS traffic. Attack scenarios encompass Brute Force, Heartbleed, Botnet, Denial of Service (DoS), Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS), Web application attacks, and internal network infiltration, representing a broad range of real-world threats. Data collection spanned 10 days, with features extracted and stored as date-labeled CSV files. Upon merging, the resulting dataset revealed a significant imbalance, with benign packets vastly outnumbering attack packets. Furthermore, the distribution of attack types is uneven; for example, the DDOS-HOIC count is approximately 10^5 times larger than SQL injection

counts, potentially impacting model classification performance. Notably, this dataset focuses solely on statistical flow characteristics, omitting payload and flow behavior analysis.

Label	Count
Benign	13425831
DDOS attack-HOIC	686012
DDoS attacks-LOIC-HTTP	576191
DoS attacks-Hulk	461912
Bot	286191
FTP-Bruteforce	193354
SSH-BruteForce	187589
Infiltration	161096
DoS attacks-SlowHTTPTest	139890
DoS attacks-GoldenEye	41508
DoS attacks-Slowloris	10990
DDOS attack-LOIC-UDP	1730
Brute Force -Web	611
Brute Force -XSS	230
SQL Injection	87

Figure 7 Labels in the UNB-IDS2018 dataset and their respective counts.

6. SYSTEM DESIGN

The flow chart in the following page describes our approach towards building a Machine Learning NIDS model. Initially the packets within the network are fed to a packet extractor to extract all its features and create a dataset. Then this dataset is pre-processed and all the relevant features are separated from others. This forms a dataset ready to be used for training the classifier models. Further multiple classifiers are trained and tested upon to select among those which perform the best in various performance metrics. The best one is selected as the NIDS Classifier. This will be further utilized in the next phase where it would be tested against adversarial inputs to check its robustness and improve upon further.

Figure 8 System Design for NIDS Classifier

7. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

7.1 Data Preprocessing

Data preprocessing by changing the labels to only two types ‘Benign’ and ‘Malicious’ as it helps to analyse the model predictions better in terms of ROC-AUC Curve. We analysed model prediction accuracy with respect to the benchmark dataset NSL-KDD.

7.2 Training with Machine learning model

Various models were tried out to have a model with best result metrics for the dataset. The best model was then used as the target model for which the adversarial inputs had to be tested to check its change in performance.

7.3 Generating adversarial inputs for UNB-IDS

Larger datasets require different methods as the whole dataset cannot be loaded into the memory at one go. For this purpose, we used PySpark Library which provides the BigData framework to work with the dataset. The same methods were used to test the models trained with the UNB Dataset having larger training times.

7.4 Generating adversarial inputs for NSL-KDD

The above process led us to have a Random Forest (RF) model which had the best metrics. Adversarial Robustness Toolbox library was used for testing the Neural Network Model as well as Random Forest Model against adversarial inputs. The adversarial white box techniques like FGSM and JSMA were used and they effectively brought down the accuracy in prediction. Transferability property was used to test adversarial inputs with Model trained with Random Forest as the white box techniques are supported only in Gradient based algorithms like Artificial Neural Networks.

The Figure 9 shows a snippet of the original NSL-KDD dataset without the perturbations or adversary added. Small perturbations are added to this dataset using the two methods FGMA and JSMA for generating adversarial inputs.

dst_host_srv_diff_host_rate	dst_host_serror_rate	dst_host_srv_serr_rate	dst_host_rerror_rate	dst_host_srv_rerror_rate	Protocol	Service	Flag	
0.00	0.0	0.0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.5	0.782609	0.9
0.00	0.0	0.0	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.0	0.637681	0.9
0.00	0.2	0.0	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.5	0.275362	0.9
0.00	1.0	1.0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.5	0.710145	0.5
0.00	0.0	0.0	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.0	0.173913	0.9
...
0.00	0.0	0.0	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.0	0.173913	0.9
0.00	1.0	1.0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.5	0.710145	0.5
0.00	0.0	0.0	1.00	0.00	1.00	0.5	0.710145	0.1
0.00	0.0	0.0	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.5	0.347826	0.9
0.02	0.0	0.0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.5	0.782609	0.9

Figure 9 Original test input snippet

The Figure 10 image shows the adversarial inputs generated by using the FGMA method. As it can be seen that this method adds a small perturbation from the values in the above image and these small perturbations cause the Intrusion Detection System to misclassify the packets.

dst_host_srv_diff_host_rate	dst_host_serror_rate	dst_host_srv_serr_rate	dst_host_rerror_rate	dst_host_srv_rerror_rate	Protocol	Service	Flag	
0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.49	0.772609	0.89
0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.99	0.627681	0.91
0.01	0.19	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.51	0.285362	0.91
0.01	0.99	1.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.51	0.720145	0.51
0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.99	0.183913	0.91
...
0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.99	0.183913	0.89
0.01	0.99	1.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.51	0.720145	0.51
0.01	0.00	0.01	0.99	0.00	0.99	0.51	0.720145	0.11
0.00	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.49	0.357826	0.89
0.03	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.49	0.772609	0.89

Figure 10 Sample Adversarial input generation test input(FGSM)

The Figure 11 shows the adversarial inputs generated by using the JSMA method. As it can be seen that his method also adds a small perturbation but uses a different function for deciding the amount of perturbation to be added and these perturbations also cause the Intrusion Detection system to misclassify.

dst_host_srv_diff_host_rate	dst_host_serror_rate	dst_host_srv_serr_rate	dst_host_rerror_rate	dst_host_srv_rerror_rate	Protocol	Service	Flag
0.00	1.00	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5 0.072464	0.5
0.03	0.00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5 0.347826	0.9
0.22	0.00	0.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.347826	0.1
0.00	0.00	0.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.710145	0.1
0.03	0.00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5 0.347826	0.9
...
0.05	0.00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5 0.347826	0.9
0.05	0.01	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5 0.347826	0.9
0.07	0.00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5 0.347826	0.9
0.00	0.00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5 0.347826	0.9
0.04	0.00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5 0.347826	0.9

Figure 11 Sample adversarial input generation test input(JSMA)

7.5 Main Algorithms used

7.5.1 Artificial Neural Networks:

There was a need for a complex classifier so the ANN model was tried. DNN was created with three dense layers with ReLU activation function and at last added a layer with a number of classes nodes. Multiple class cross entropy was used as a loss function with Adam Optimizer. Results were favourable and better than any classifier were trained and tested for.

7.5.2 Random Forest:

There was an effort to search better models compared to ANN, so Random Forest (RF) Algorithm was tried which takes in multiple decision trees into account. The number of estimators (Decision Trees) are kept by default provided by Python which is set to 100. This model is trained and tested which resulted in excellent metric values.

7.5.3 Fast Gradient Sign Method:

Fast Gradient Sign Method is a brute force adversarial input generation technique that tries to perturb the input data values and make the model miss-classify the output. This method is cost-effective as it tries to add perturbation to every input value and checks which causes the maximum prediction error.

7.5.4 Jacobian Saliency Map Method:

JSMA uses saliency features to sort the columns based on which property helps to misclassify the output the most. This is a costly method and could be run with only the smaller dataset to time constraints

7.6 Implementation

Incoming network traffic filled with packets was extracted and converted into the data which can be used for implementing models. This was done using CIC Flowmeter which helped us to convert packets into a feature structured dataset.

Next was to analyse the data and pre-process it. Extraction of principal features was performed using PCA which explained significant variance. These principal features(components) help classifiers better perform and reduce the complexity of the classifiers by decreasing the number of features to be trained on.

Now the next step was to select a few classifiers which could be trained on and tested. Some of the typical classifiers were chosen among many which work better on the multi-class classification.

The test was first done with the most basic type of classifier- Naive Bayes (NB) Classifier which is the most generic form of classifier available. But this classifier wasn't effective as it wasn't taking into account interdependence of features which is generally the case in most of the dataset.

Figure 12 Algorithm for Naive Bayes Classifier for Binary Classifier[1]

Following that another popular classifier Support Vector Machines (SVM) was used. The dataset was trained with the hyperparameter of the kernel as the Radial Basis Function (RBF) which typically works well with multiple features for constructing decision boundaries in the higher dimensions. This gave better results than NB classifier but wasn't up to the mark, a classifier was needed to identify almost all the positive attacks. So other kernels were tried but that didn't yield better results than RBF.

```

Data : Dataset with  $p^*$  variables and binary outcome.
Output: Ranked list of variables according to their relevance.

Find the optimal values for the tuning parameters of the SVM model;
Train the SVM model;
 $p \leftarrow p^*$ ;
while  $p \geq 2$  do
     $SVM_p \leftarrow$  SVM with the optimized tuning parameters for the  $p$  variables and
    observations in Data;
     $w_p \leftarrow$  calculate weight vector of the  $SVM_p$  ( $w_{p1}, \dots, w_{pp}$ );
     $rank.criteria \leftarrow (w_{p1}^2, \dots, w_{pp}^2)$ ;
     $min.rank.criteria \leftarrow$  variable with lowest value in  $rank.criteria$  vector;
    Remove  $min.rank.criteria$  from Data;
     $Rank_p \leftarrow min.rank.criteria$ ;
     $p \leftarrow p - 1$ ;
end
 $Rank_1 \leftarrow$  variable in Data  $\notin (Rank_2, \dots, Rank_{p^*})$ ;
return ( $Rank_1, \dots, Rank_{p^*}$ )

```

Figure 13 Algorithm for SVM Classifier for Binary Classifier [17].

There was a need for a complex classifier, so the ANN model was tried. DNN was created with three dense layers with ReLU activation function and at last added a layer with several classes nodes. Multiple class cross entropy was used as a loss function with Adam Optimizer. Results were favourable and better than any classifier were trained and tested for.

Algorithm 1 Backpropagation Algorithm

```

1: procedure TRAIN
2:    $X \leftarrow$  Training Data Set of size  $m \times n$ 
3:    $y \leftarrow$  Labels for records in  $X$ 
4:    $w \leftarrow$  The weights for respective layers
5:    $l \leftarrow$  The number of layers in the neural network,  $1 \dots L$ 
6:    $D_{ij}^{(l)} \leftarrow$  The error for all  $l, i, j$ 
7:    $t_{ij}^{(l)} \leftarrow 0$ . For all  $l, i, j$ 
8:   For  $i = 1$  to  $m$ 
9:      $a^l \leftarrow feedforward(x^{(i)}, w)$ 
10:     $d^l \leftarrow a(L) - y^{(i)}$ 
11:     $t_{ij}^{(l)} \leftarrow t_{ij}^{(l)} + a_j^{(l)} \cdot t_i^{l+1}$ 
12:    if  $j \neq 0$  then
13:       $D_{ij}^{(l)} \leftarrow \frac{1}{m} t_{ij}^{(l)} + \lambda w_{ij}^{(l)}$ 
14:    else
15:       $D_{ij}^{(l)} \leftarrow \frac{1}{m} t_{ij}^{(l)}$ 
16:    where  $\frac{\partial}{\partial w_{ij}^{(l)}} J(w) = D_{ij}^{(l)}$ 

```

Figure 14 Backpropagation Algorithm used in ANN [18].

There was an effort to search better models compared to ANN, so Random Forest (RF) Algorithm was tried which takes in multiple decision trees into account. The number of estimators (Decision Trees) are kept by default provided by Python which is set to 100. This model is trained and tested which resulted in excellent metric values.

Figure 15 Random Forest algorithm used [19]

Therefore, after carefully examining the performances of various classifiers, it was inferred that ANN and RF models perform better than other tried out classifiers. So, in further steps both these models were considered to check further which of these perform better against the Adversarial inputs. And the better performing model will be chosen to further improve upon.

8. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The training and testing results of various models used for the two datasets are given below.

8.1 NSL KDD Dataset

8.1.1 Neural Networks

The below figure shows the shape of the data and the different kinds of labels and their particular number of data points for each label for training the neural network.

```
Shapes of training and testing are: (125973, 43) (22544, 43)
Unique Labels ['normal' 'DOS' 'R2L' 'Probe' 'U2R']
Model: "sequential_1"
-----
Layer (type)                Output Shape          Param #
-----
dense_3 (Dense)              (None, 256)           31488
dropout_2 (Dropout)          (None, 256)           0
dense_4 (Dense)              (None, 256)           65792
dropout_3 (Dropout)          (None, 256)           0
dense_5 (Dense)              (None, 5)             1285
-----
Total params: 98,565
Trainable params: 98,565
Non-trainable params: 0
```

Figure 16 Neural Network on NSL-KDD information

```
Epoch 1/5
3937/3937 [=====] - 8s 2ms/step - loss: 0.0638 - accuracy: 0.9795
Epoch 2/5
3937/3937 [=====] - 8s 2ms/step - loss: 0.0319 - accuracy: 0.9886
Epoch 3/5
3937/3937 [=====] - 8s 2ms/step - loss: 0.0264 - accuracy: 0.9908
Epoch 4/5
3937/3937 [=====] - 7s 2ms/step - loss: 0.0236 - accuracy: 0.9919
Epoch 5/5
3937/3937 [=====] - 7s 2ms/step - loss: 0.0222 - accuracy: 0.9927
705/705 [=====] - 1s 940us/step - loss: 0.0159 - accuracy: 0.9945
Accuracy : 99.44552779197693
```

Figure 17 Neural Network Training and Testing accuracy on NSL KDD

The [above](#) figure shows all the 5 epochs that were done in the training of the neural network along with the accuracies on the NSL-KDD dataset with a fairly good amount of accuracy.

8.1.2 Random Forest

```
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier

#Create a Gaussian Classifier
clf=RandomForestClassifier(n_estimators=1)

#Train the model using the training sets y_pred=clf.predict(X_test)
clf.fit(X_train_scaled,y_train)

y_pred=clf.predict(X_test_scaled)
#print("Accuracy : ",scores[1]*100)
```

```
from sklearn import metrics
# Model Accuracy, how often is the classifier correct?
print("Accuracy:",metrics.accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred))
```

```
Accuracy: 0.9953424414478353
```

Figure 18 Random Forest Accuracy and ROC Curve score on NSL KDD

Multiple Decision Trees(DT) trained in the RF model which are then voted out for classifying an input works well with large dataset and multiple features and evidently provided us with excellent results of near perfect score on accuracy.

8.1.3. Linear SVM:

```
#Create a svm Classifier
clf = svm.SVC(kernel='linear') # Linear Kernel
#print(y_train)

#Train the model using the training sets
clf.fit(X_train_scaled, y_train)

#Predict the response for test dataset
y_pred = clf.predict(X_test_scaled)
```

Output Hidden

```
from sklearn import metrics
# Model Accuracy: how often is the classifier correct?
print("Accuracy:",metrics.accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred))
```

```
Accuracy: 0.9816359119943222
```

Figure 19 Linear SVM Accuracy and Confusion matrix on NSL KDD

SVM classifier for multiple features generally requires a kernel function for creating a multidimensional hyperplane for separating classes. But in our case linear kernel gave promising results compared to other standard kernel functions like RBF etc. But weren't sufficient to better the RF model.

8.1.4 Comparison of Testing Accuracies of different Algorithms :

Figure 20 Graphical Comparison of different algorithms on NSL KDD

8.2 UNB-IDS 2018 :

8.2.1 Random Forest :

Figure 21 Random Forest Metrics on UNB-IDS 2018 Dataset

The above figure gives the different kinds of accuracies and measurables used for testing the performance of the model like F1 score, Accuracy, weighted precision & recall etc. The Random Forest proved to be a very suitable model for the dataset and gave very high accuracies.

8.2.2 Multinomial Logistic Regression :

F1 Score	:0.7529641875432465
Accuracy	:0.8300484833527706
Weighted Precision	:0.6889804847162347
Weighted Recall	:0.8300484833527706
Weighted True Positive Rate	:0.8300484833527706
Weighted False Positive Rate	:0.8300484833527706
Weighted F Measure	:0.7529641875432465

Figure 22 Multinomial Logistic Regression on UNB-IDS 2018 Dataset

The various measurables which were used in the random forest were also used in the multinomial Logistic Regression for the UNB dataset which could not match with the performance of the Random forest but performed better than some of the other existing models.

8.2.3 Comparison of different Classification metrics of the models trained:

Figure 23 Graphical Comparison of performance of both the Algorithms

It can be clearly seen that random forest performs better than Multinomial Logistic Regression(MLR) in every aspect but a major difference can be seen in the weighted false positive rate which is significantly higher in MLR which is not desirable. So it can clearly be seen that the RF classifier works well for both the datasets which it was trained on than any other classifier which was tried out.

8.3 NSL-KDD Dataset with adversary using FGSM and JSMA

Figure 24 Accuracy measures for neural network using FGSM adversary

The Figure 24 clearly shows effects of the perturbation in the input data can be clearly seen in the decrease in the accuracy. But furthermore increase in the perturbation increases the accuracy because the data then starts to resemble the existing genuine data which model has seen or has become robust to.

Figure 25 Accuracy measures for neural network using JSMA adversary

The Figure 25 depicts a drop in the accuracy of the model for the JSMA attack is drastic because it targets particular feature values which influence the most in the decision making. Hence even the small perturbation has drastic impact.

Random Forest Testing using FGSM

Figure 26 Accuracy measures for random forest using FGSM adversary

The Figure 26 also shows the influence of the FGSM attack is similar to that seen in the Neural Network model. The accuracy keeps decreasing as the perturbations are increased.

Random Forest Testing using JSMA

Figure 27 Accuracy measures for random forest using JSMA adversary

It can also be seen in Figure 27 that FGSM influence on the Random Forest is almost the same as seen for the Neural Network model. This also proves the assumption that the adversaries created with the NN as the target model also extrapolate to the RF model as well. Hence, transferability property holds good here.

8.4 FGSM Adversarial Attack on model trained with UNB-IDS Dataset

UNB-IDS dataset is the latest and updated dataset compared to the NSL-KDD dataset. Adversarial inputs are generated using FGSM on UNB-IDS dataset and tested against Neural Network and Random Forest Machine learning models.

The following graphs depict the accuracies for Neural Network and Random Forest.

It is observed that the accuracies of the trained model against adversarial inputs is robust as it has seen a larger variation of random unique data as seen in Figure 28 The same is observed for random forest in Figure 27

Figure 28 Accuracy measures for Neural Network using FGSM adversary(UNB-IDS dataset)

Figure 29 Accuracy measures for random forest using FGSM adversary(UNB-IDS dataset)

9. CONCLUSION

The conducted experiments underscore the vulnerabilities of anomaly-based Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) to adversarial inputs, particularly in scenarios involving online learning. The findings reveal that the classification behavior of such systems can be systematically influenced by altering certain attribute values in the packet feature set. While models trained on smaller datasets like NSL-KDD exhibited reduced robustness and higher susceptibility to poisoning attacks, larger datasets such as UNB-IDS improved model resilience due to their capacity to better capture data diversity and complexities.

The promising performance of machine learning techniques, such as Random Forest (achieving 95% accuracy), highlights their potential in anomaly-based IDS. However, the experiments also stress that no machine learning algorithm is entirely secure, as attackers with insights into training attributes can exploit vulnerabilities to manipulate classification outcomes.

These results emphasize the importance of adopting robust defenses against adversarial attacks in anomaly-based IDS, such as incorporating techniques for detecting and mitigating poisoned inputs. The study also suggests exploring innovative and adaptive strategies, including bio-inspired response systems, to enhance the

resilience of anomaly-based IDS against evolving threats. The continuous research in this field remains vital for ensuring the security and reliability of networks in the face of increasingly sophisticated attack methodologies.

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